

Figure ES1: a. Energy-magnitude station corrections δS (Bindi et al, Energy-magnitude station corrections across the conterminous United States, submitted to Bull. Seism. Soc. Am.) and physiographic regions of the conterminous United States; b. Normalized Rayleigh attenuation values at the 3s period (redrawn after Magrini et al., 2021); c the same as b but for 6s; d the same as b but for 12s.